

Environmental Impacts in the Passenger Road Transport System in Rio de Janeiro City

*Impactos Ambientais no Sistema de Transporte Rodoviário de
Passageiros na Cidade do Rio de Janeiro*
*Impactos Ambientales en el Sistema de Transporte por Carretera
de Pasajeros en la Ciudad de Río de Janeiro*

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Abstract: This article presents an analysis of the environmental impacts in the urban road passenger transport sector in the city of Rio de Janeiro, as well as the measures adopted by the sector to mitigate these effects. Initially, an overview of the sector was provided, followed by an analysis of the Brazilian legislation applicable to it and a presentation of the main environmental impacts caused by the sector in the urban environment in which it operates. The study is justified by the need to deepen the understanding of environmental impacts in transportation and to offer substantive contributions toward finding solutions that reconcile urban development with environmental preservation and the promotion of societal well-being.

Keywords: *Sustainable mobility; Urban road passenger transport; Environmental impacts; Sustainable cities.*

Resumo: Este artigo apresenta uma análise dos impactos ambientais no setor de transporte rodoviário urbano da cidade do Rio de Janeiro, bem como as medidas do setor para atenuar seus efeitos. Inicialmente, foi feito um panorama do setor, seguido de uma análise da legislação brasileira aplicada ao setor e a apresentação dos principais impactos ambientais ocasionados pelo setor no meio urbano em que está inserido. O estudo é justificado pela necessidade de se aprofundar a compreensão dos impactos ambientais no transporte e oferecer contribuições substantivas para a busca de soluções que harmonizem o desenvolvimento urbano com a preservação do meio ambiente e a promoção do bem-estar da sociedade.

Palavras-chave: Mobilidade sustentável; Transporte rodoviário urbano de passageiros; Impactos Ambientais; Cidades sustentáveis.

Resumen: Este artículo presenta un análisis de los impactos ambientales en el sector del transporte urbano de pasajeros por carretera en la ciudad de Río de Janeiro, así como las medidas adoptadas por el sector para atenuar dichos efectos. Inicialmente, se ofrece un panorama del sector, seguido de un análisis de la legislación brasileña aplicable y la presentación de los principales impactos ambientales ocasionados por el sector en el entorno urbano en el que se encuentra. El estudio se justifica por la necesidad de profundizar en la comprensión de los impactos ambientales en el transporte y de aportar contribuciones substantivas para la búsqueda de soluciones

Recebido

Received

Recibido

18 out. 2025

Oct 18, 2025

12 otu. 2025

Aceito

Accepted

Aceptado

08 nov. 2025

Nov 08, 2025

08 nov. 2025

Publicado

Published

Publicado

15 nov. 2025

Nov 15, 2025

15 nov. 2025

<https://git.fateczl.edu.br>

e_ISSN

2965-3339

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.20171187

São Paulo

v. 4 | n. 1

v. 4 | i. 1

e41393

Outubro/Dezembro

Octubre/December

Octubre/Diciembre

2025

que armonicen el desarrollo urbano con la preservación del medio ambiente y la promoción del bienestar social.

Palabras clave: *Movilidad sostenible; Transporte urbano de pasajeros por carretera; Impactos ambientales; Ciudades sostenibles.*

1. INTRODUCTION

To understand the metamorphosis that urban space undergoes, it is necessary to begin with the reasoning that, broadly speaking, urban centers tend to occupy unexplored territories and expand their boundaries. This process represents a continuous adaptation of the urban environment to accommodate new practices and ventures, while seeking to shorten distances more efficiently. The analysis of the global evolution of transportation systems demonstrates this pursuit of growth and adaptation. In this context, urban mobility and the expansion of cities are interconnected, and understanding this dynamic is essential for planning and creating more sustainable and effective cities for the present and future (Sepulveda). Barino; Cunha; Barino, 2025).

Urban growth is correlated with an increase in the urbanization rate, defined as the proportion of the urban population relative to the total population. In contrast to Europe, which experienced urbanization during the 19th century, driven by the Industrial Revolution, Brazil began its urbanization in the 20th century at an accelerated pace, due to internal and external migrations. This temporal distinction in the urbanization process played a critical role in shaping Brazil's current urban landscape, necessitating a careful, context-specific approach to the challenges and opportunities that arise (Silveira, 2004).

Concern about urban environmental problems in Brazil emerged alongside the growth of cities and the expansion of the motor vehicle fleet, a concern that was not present until the 1970s. The relationship between urban development and passenger transport affects the environment and plays a critical role in the economic, social, and environmental development of cities. However, the increase in the fleet has led to a series of environmental problems, including congestion on urban roads, air pollution, soil and groundwater contamination from vehicle deterioration, and inadequate waste management. These problems are aggravated by the absence of effective public policies and a lack of environmental awareness (Pereira et al., 2021).

The observation of this scenario in large cities reinforces the view that modernization and urban evolution constitute a major management challenge. Urban expansion and urbanization have consequences for the environment, and an emblematic example is urban transport systems and the environmental problems they pose. Therefore, addressing urban growth through proactive management to mitigate environmental impacts and promote sustainable development helps ensure a healthy urban society (Mattos, 2001).

Poor mobility systems exacerbate socio-spatial disparities and strain the urban environmental balance. Infrastructure and transport quality, in turn, impact mobility and accessibility. In this context, environmental legislation plays a role in regulating passenger transport services, establishing guidelines for their organization, discipline, and oversight by public authorities, based on minimum requirements involving safety, comfort, hygiene, and service quality (Maia et al, 2019).

Given the complex interactions among urban growth, passenger transport, and the environment, this article aimed to present the main environmental impacts

of urban road transport in Rio de Janeiro. The analysis sought a holistic understanding of these impacts, considering their implications and viable strategies for their mitigation.

The rationale for this study lies in the growing importance of environmental issues and the need to understand their impacts in the urban context. Its relevance aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, specifically Goal 11, which addresses sustainable cities and communities.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research adopts a qualitative, applied, exploratory approach to understanding and interpreting complex phenomena across different areas of knowledge, with the purpose of providing support for immediate practical application and being directed towards solving a specific problem. To achieve the research objective, a survey of documentary and bibliographic content was conducted, which serves as the basis for the analysis.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Urban Road passenger transport in the city of Rio de Janeiro

The growth of the city of Rio de Janeiro was shaped by the region's unique geography, situated between mountains, the sea, lagoons, and swamps. This growth occurred predominantly in the flat areas between these geographical features and developed in a relatively disorganized manner, directly impacting the city's public transportation system. As the city grew, transportation services were established to meet the increasing demands, but without planning that prioritized urban mobility. Thus, these services adapted to the emerging road network and subsequently underwent urbanization processes (Valente, 2017).

The Rio de Janeiro Metropolitan Region, comprising 21 municipalities, has a comprehensive public passenger transport system that includes various modes, such as urban trains, taxis, metro, BRTs, light rail, vans, ferries, and conventional bus lines. This system plays a central role in the population's mobility, serving approximately 80% of trips in the region during the pre-pandemic period. However, the complexity of its operation is evident, since, despite the existence of a Metropolitan Transport Agency, each municipality maintains responsibility for the exclusive bus and van lines within its territory. On the other hand, the State assumes the management of trains, metro, ferries, and intermunicipal bus and van lines. This diversity of responsibilities highlights the importance of effective coordination among governance bodies to improve the integration and efficiency of this transport system, with the aim of meeting the population's needs in a more adequate and sustainable way (Ministry of Transport, 2019).

It is evident that the transportation system in the municipality of Rio de Janeiro is significantly influenced by the neighboring municipalities that make up the Rio de Janeiro Metropolitan Region. This influence is reflected in the

composition of the transportation modes used. In the municipality of Rio de Janeiro, municipal bus transportation accounts for the largest share, followed by alternative transportation (such as vans) and intercity transportation. In the Rio de Janeiro Metropolitan Region, the scenario is different, with intercity bus transportation having the largest share (SMT, 2006).

The city of Rio de Janeiro currently has a public transportation infrastructure comprising 2,395 kilometers of routes, with an average of 1,517,000 trips per day and a total of 553,591,000 passengers per day (City Transit Data, 2023). This volume totals 32 million passengers transported, equivalent to 1 million trips completed each month. To sustain this demand, a fleet of 3,500 vehicles operating on weekdays consumes 8 million liters of diesel fuel, distributed across 296 lines subdivided into 8 distinct services (Rio Ônibus, 2023).

The operation of this public transport infrastructure is organized into four distinct consortia comprising 29 companies: the Internorte Consortium, the Transcarioca Consortium, the Santa Cruz Consortium, and the Intersul Consortium. These consortia are groups of companies that previously operated individually on specific routes, aiming to improve the efficiency and coverage of public transport across different regions of the city (Rio Ônibus, 2023a).

3.2 Main legal bases for the right to public transportation in Brazil

The right to transportation was thus expressly considered a social right in Brazil after Constitutional Amendment No. 90, of September 15, 2015, which included it in Article 6 of the Brazilian Constitution of 1988, consolidating its position as a fundamental right and, consequently, an entrenched clause of the national constitutional order, in light of the provisions of Article 60, paragraph 4, item IV, of the national political charter (Brazil, 1988).

As a social right, transportation plays a strategic role because it serves as a means for the implementation of several other fundamental rights, such as education, health, food, leisure, and mobility, among others, fulfilling an undeniable social function and pointing towards the corollary of human dignity (Lenza, 2016).

The right to transportation expresses one of the vital basic needs to be guaranteed to Brazilian workers, to the point of being literally included as one of the expenses to be considered, at least programmatically, in the calculation of the nationally stipulated value for the minimum wage in Brazil, according to Article 7, item IV of the Constitution (Brazil, 1988).

Therefore, even before the express inclusion of transportation in the list of social rights, there were already indications, in the 1988 Republican Constitution itself, of the fundamental nature of this right, since it was mentioned in the aforementioned Article 7, as well as in Article 208, item VII (which points out as a duty of the State the provision of transportation to students), in Article 227, paragraph 2 (which requires accessibility regulations for people with disabilities in public transportation), in Article 230, paragraph 2

(which determines free access for those over sixty-five years of age in urban public transportation) and in Article 244 (general constitutional provision that emphasizes the issue of accessibility for people with disabilities also in public transportation (Brazil, 1988).

Given the importance of transportation, with the emphasis given in this article to urban road-based public transportation, it is legally classified as an essential service or activity, as outlined in Article 10, item V, and Article 11 of Federal Law No. 7,783 of 1989, so that, for the purposes of exercising the right to strike, unions, employers, and workers, by mutual agreement, are obliged to guarantee the provision of such services, even during the strike, due to the urgent needs of the community (BRAZIL, 1989).

Within the framework of the distribution of federal constitutional powers, based essentially on the principle of the predominance of interests, in terms of the topic of "transportation," it is seen that the Union has the material competence to directly operate, or through authorization, concession, or permission, interstate and international road passenger transport services, according to Article 21, item XX, letter "e," as well as the competence of the Union to establish guidelines for urban development, including with regard to urban transport, in accordance with Article 21, item XX, both of the 1988 Federal Constitution (Brazil, 1988).

Regarding legislative powers over transportation, the Union receives from the Constitution the exclusive mandate to legislate on the guidelines of the national transportation policy (Article 22, item IX), as well as to legislate on traffic and transportation (Article 22, item XI), both articles contained in the 1988 Constitution. As for Brazilian municipalities, according to Article 30, item V, the legislative power over public transportation allows them, at the municipal level, to regulate the organization and provision of essential public services, including public transportation, either directly or under a concession or permit regime. Still within the current constitutional text, in the chapter that discusses the general principles of economic activity, it is worth highlighting that the regulation of land transport is a matter subject to legal reserve, and, regarding the regulation of international transport, the agreements signed by the Union must be observed, respecting the principle of reciprocity, in accordance with Article 178 of the 1988 Constitution (Jus, 2023).

3.3 Environmental legislation applied to the transport sector

Brazilian environmental legislation is a pillar of environmental preservation, aiming to mitigate the negative impacts of human activities on the environment. These laws are monitored by environmental entities at the federal, state, and municipal levels, which establish regulations and enforcement measures to ensure compliance. The inclusion of environmental issues in the 1988 Federal Constitution, specifically in Article 225, marked a significant advance in environmental concern, establishing that an ecologically

balanced environment is a right of all and a shared responsibility between the Public Authorities and society. This legal framework reflects the country's commitment to environmental protection and the promotion of sustainable development (IBF, 2023).

Brazilian environmental legislation is globally recognized as one of the most comprehensive, not limited to preservation, but also incorporating measures to mitigate the environmental impacts of human activities. Thus, it plays a fundamental role in promoting sustainable development, placing the responsibility on organizations to preserve natural resources, reduce environmental impacts, and foster social development. Additionally, it exerts a significant influence on society by establishing standards of environmental conduct for citizens, consolidating its impact. Beyond its national impact, Brazilian environmental legislation serves as a model for other developing countries, facing the challenge of balancing economic growth and environmental protection (Jus, 2023).

The first environmental legislation directed at the passenger transport sector in Brazil was Federal Law No. 6,938/1981, which established the National Environmental Policy. Although this law did not focus exclusively on passenger transport, it established general principles and guidelines for protecting the environment in all its forms, addressing issues such as air and noise pollution, which significantly impact public transport. This legislation established a basis for regulating and overseeing activities that affect the environment, including transport. As society matured and awareness of environmental issues became a matter of public interest, additional laws and regulations were enacted to address specific aspects of road passenger transport and its interaction with the environment in which it operates (MMA, 1981).

The Brazilian legal framework is extensive and complex, encompassing various spheres of government. To present in an organized manner the main Brazilian laws specific to public transportation, at the federal, state, and municipal levels, Table 1 was created to clearly and systematically display these regulations, allowing for an understanding of the laws applicable to public transportation in the city of Rio de Janeiro, and aiding in the analysis and compliance with environmental regulations related to this sector.

Table 1 - Main transport sector legislation applicable to the city of Rio de Janeiro.

Local authority	Legislation	Purpose
Federal	CONAMA Resolution No. 001/1986	Establish criteria and standards for air pollutant emissions from motor vehicles.
Federal	CONAMA Resolution No.	It establishes criteria for environmental licensing

	418/2009	of road and rail terminals.
Federal	Federal Law No. 12.587/2012	Establishes the guidelines for the National Urban Mobility Policy, setting principles and guidelines for sustainable public transportation.
State	INEA-RJ Resolution No. 19/2012	Define the procedures for environmental licensing of bus terminals in the state.
State	INEA-RJ Normative Instruction No. 07/2015	Regulates the preparation of Environmental Impact Studies (EIA) and Environmental Impact Reports (RIMA) for road projects.
Municipal	SMAC Resolution No. 215/2007	Defines guidelines for the environmental licensing of bus terminals and garages of road passenger transport companies in the city.
Municipal	Normative Instruction SMAC No. 03/2008	Regulates procedures for environmental licensing of bus terminals and road passenger transport companies in the municipality.

Source: the authors (2025).

3.4 Environmental impacts caused by urban road passenger transport in the city of Rio de Janeiro

The transportation sector is emerging as a driver of environmental pollution in urban centers, a trend outpacing GDP growth in developing countries. This scenario is driven by the intensified use of natural resources, particularly fossil fuels, whose emissions are deteriorating environmental quality and causing significant environmental damage (Kojima; Lovei, 2000; Assumpção et al., 2000; Mattos, 2001).

The predominance of road transport in passenger transportation, with a 96% share, implies high energy demand, mainly petroleum derivatives, making the transportation sector a significant source of potential air pollution. Road transport also plays a considerable role in freight transport in Brazil. Although road transport is also relevant in freight transport, its share is lower than that of passenger transport (Mattos, 2001).

The negative externalities associated with urban passenger transport can be extensive. In analyses and studies of this sector, some of these externalities stand out for their visibility and tangibility. Among the most notable are, but are not limited to, local and regional air pollution, the contribution to worsening climate change, congestion, pollutant emissions, traffic accidents, visual intrusion, waste generation, and associated social issues.

The implementation and maintenance of road infrastructure entail additional environmental impacts that are ignored by studies focused solely on system operation. Road construction, for example, involves significant excavation and land relocation, the suppression of extensive areas of vegetation, the modification of stormwater drainage patterns, the deposition of sediments that lead to the silting of water bodies, and the need to relocate local communities, among other adverse effects. These considerations highlight the complexity and

scope of the impacts associated with the development and operation of road infrastructure, requiring a careful and integrated approach to transport management.

3.5 Environmental impacts associated with atmospheric emissions

The urban bus fleet, a fundamental component of the urban transport system, emits air pollutants, specifically Nitrogen Oxides (NOx) and Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs), with implications for air quality, climate change and public health. Mitigation measures include fleet modernization, adopting bus models with more advanced emission-control technologies and transitioning to electric vehicles, thereby aligning with efforts to minimize the adverse effects of these emissions (Maia; Netto; Costa, 2019).

To control and mitigate the environmental impacts generated by buses, Rio Ônibus and the Federation of Mobility Companies of the State of Rio de Janeiro implemented the Green Seal program. This program was designed to monitor atmospheric pollutant emissions, in accordance with the state environmental legislation Directive DZ-572.R-4 of Procon Fumaça Preta. The program includes regular report submission and access to a database that provides information on fleet emissions measurements. This initiative, developed in collaboration with the entities and INEA-RJ, grants certifications that identify vehicles that have passed opacity tests, thereby helping to reduce the environmental impacts of public road transport (Rio Ônibus, 2023c; SEMOVE, 2023).

Another action related to the topic is the "Despoluir" program, in collaboration with the National Confederation of Transport and SEST/SENAT, which is an initiative to monitor and control gas and particulate emissions from vehicles. This effort is based on measuring emissions from the bus fleet and assessing its state of conservation (Rio Ônibus, 2023c; SEMOVE, 2023a).

3.6 Environmental impacts associated with noise pollution

Buses, especially older models, are a significant source of noise pollution in urban areas, a problem widely recognized in public transport worldwide. This issue has direct implications for the quality of life of urban residents, specifically those living near bus routes. Furthermore, prolonged exposure to bus noise can negatively affect the health of road transport workers in the medium term and disrupt wildlife in urban areas, including spaces designated for this purpose (Cavalheiro et al., 2000).

To mitigate the negative effects of this impact, the Federation of Mobility Companies of Rio de Janeiro implemented a Noise Control Program. This program involves monitoring noise emission levels and ensuring compliance with occupational safety legislation and the maximum noise pollution limits established by federal environmental legislation. This initiative aims not only to protect workers' health but also to reduce noise pollution in urban areas (Rio Ônibus, 2023c).

3.7 Environmental impacts associated with the consumption of natural resources

The use of fossil fuel-powered buses is a central concern for environmental

sustainability. These vehicles contribute to the depletion of non-renewable resources, posing a challenge to the continuity of energy supply in the future. Furthermore, the extraction, production, and combustion of fossil fuels are associated with significant environmental impacts, including the emission of air pollutants and greenhouse gases that contribute to climate change, in addition to the impacts listed previously (Maia; Netto; Costa, 2019).

Concerns about the impacts of public transportation are evident, and to address them, the Federation of Mobility Companies of Rio de Janeiro adopts Eco-efficiency programs. These programs primarily focus on consulting on alternative fuels, such as electric buses, hybrids, biofuels, and CNG, aiming to reduce emissions and reliance on non-renewable resources. Furthermore, energy efficiency consulting seeks to evaluate technologies and products that improve the energy performance of transportation companies' fleets and garages (SEMOVE, 2023a).

4 ANALYSIS

In Brazil, the right to public transportation was recognized as a social right by Constitutional Amendment No. 90/2015, which incorporated it into Article 6 of the Federal Constitution, thereby reinforcing its role as an instrument for accessing fundamental rights, including education, health, and leisure. Legislation designates public transportation as an essential service, establishing obligations even during strikes to ensure the fulfillment of the population's basic needs. In parallel, environmental regulation of the sector is broad, encompassing federal, state, and municipal norms, notably the National Environmental Policy (Law No. 6,938/1981), the National Urban Mobility Policy (Law No. 12,587/2012), and resolutions from CONAMA and INEA, which regulate pollutant emissions and terminal licensing, aiming to reduce the environmental impacts of public transportation and promote sustainable practices.

Urban road passenger transport in Rio de Janeiro is conditioned by the city's geographical configuration, marked by mountains, coastline, and wetlands, which have influenced urban development. The disorderly growth of urban space has affected the structure of the public transport system, which has expanded adaptively to the pre-existing road network, without systematic planning. In the Metropolitan Region, composed of 21 municipalities, multiple modes of transport coexist, including buses, metro, trains, ferries, and vans, which accounted for approximately 80% of urban trips before the pandemic period.

The city's public transportation infrastructure covers more than 2,395 km of routes, registering an average of 1.5 million daily trips. To meet this demand, approximately 3,500 vehicles are used, with a monthly consumption of approximately 8 million liters of diesel. The operation is conducted by four consortia comprising 29 companies to expand service coverage and organize transportation supplies across different urban regions.

Managing public transportation in the region is highly complex due to the involvement of multiple administrative levels. Municipalities are responsible for local bus and van lines, while the state oversees intercity and larger-scale modes of transport, such as trains and subways. This distribution of responsibilities demands coordinated efforts among government agencies to ensure system integration, yet it represents a persistent challenge for promoting sustainable urban mobility.

The environmental impacts of urban road passenger transport encompass multiple dimensions. The predominance of this mode, responsible for 96% of passenger transport, results in high demand for fossil fuels, contributing to air, noise, and visual pollution, waste generation, and increased congestion. The construction and maintenance of the road network also cause environmental changes, such as deforestation, alterations to waterways, and community displacement. Emissions from the bus fleet include pollutants such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and volatile organic compounds (VOCs), with direct impacts on air quality and public health. To reduce these effects, programs such as the Green Seal, which monitors vehicle emissions, and the Depollute program, which assesses fleet conservation and coordinates pollutant control actions in partnership with SEST/SENAT and the National Confederation of Transport, have been implemented. Noise pollution has a significant impact on urban transportation, especially from the operation of older buses, affecting the quality of life of residents along the routes and potentially compromising the hearing health of workers in the sector. To mitigate this effect, the Noise Control Program was established to monitor noise levels and ensure compliance with environmental and occupational safety standards.

Finally, the high consumption of natural resources, especially fossil fuels, poses a challenge to sustainability, contributing to the depletion of non-renewable reserves and intensifying climate change. In this context, the Federation of Mobility Companies of Rio de Janeiro has implemented eco-efficiency programs to adopt alternative fuels and technologies that improve energy performance and reduce environmental impacts.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This article aims to present the environmental impacts resulting from the road passenger transport system in the city of Rio de Janeiro. The text initially addressed the context of urban passenger transport in Rio de Janeiro, followed by an analysis of Brazilian environmental legislation applicable to the sector and the laws safeguarding citizens' right to transportation. Finally, the main environmental impacts of this mode of transport in the studied city were detailed, along with the actions undertaken to mitigate them.

The topic encompasses a wide range of issues, characterized by complexity, particularly due to the ongoing evolution of sustainable development and urban sustainability concepts, as well as the maturation of environmental legislation. However, it is important to recognize that it is not possible to fully map the impacts associated with the subject, since studies and actions related

to environmental issues in the transport sector often do not include a complete and integrated analysis of the supply chain involved in road construction, the manufacture of transport equipment, and others.

This study contributes to a greater understanding of the environmental challenges associated with road passenger transport, highlighting the importance of mitigating and sustainable measures to address these impacts.

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